

On Cardinality of Infinite Sets

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Chapter 0:

Introduction

The main goal of this paper is to map each element in an infinitely large set X to one natural number, amongst other proofs and conclusions of similar nature.

Georg Cantor's 'proof' that there are more real numbers between 0 and 1 than there are natural numbers involves the "diagonal argument".

We will start off by listing every real number in range $[0, 1)$:

0.738457583475837583758347589347 . . .

0.938274897482374274328947284722 . . .

0.673427348283492384648978934898 . . .

0.521353478532874287238748923742 . . .

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. .
.

Then, take the first decimal digit of the first number(in this case 7) and replace it with any other digit. Then, take the second digit of the second number's decimal and do the same. Continue doing the same for every number and change the i -th decimal digit. If we then take all the new digits and form the number

$0.d_1d_2d_3d_4d_5d_6d_7\dots d_i\dots$

we notice that the newly formed number has at least one digit of difference from all other written numbers, therefore we have found a number which was not already written, hence the real numbers are uncountable.

The main flaw with this method is that it gives the same results with natural numbers, which, by definition, are countable. This means that:

1. Each real number written in the list can be mapped to one natural number by using the method described in the following chapter.
2. Using the diagonal argument, we can find a natural number n which was not written on the list. In other words, we find a natural number n which does not map to any real number from range $[0, 1)$ which was written in the list of every real number from that range.

With this we conclude that the set of \mathbf{N} is larger than the set of numbers between 0 and 1. In further chapters we will discuss why this is also incorrect.

Chapter 1:

Bijection between natural numbers and real numbers between 0 and 1

The 'proof' there are more numbers in range $[0, 1)$ than there are in the \mathbf{N} set is simply false, which was demonstrated in the previous chapter.

Take any number in the $[0, 1)$ range. For this demonstration I will use the number 0.123. We need to ask ourselves an important question: "How do the real numbers between 0 and 1 differ from the natural numbers?" There are 2 differences:

1. They have "0." preceding them.
2. Adding zeros to either side does the opposite on the two sets. This means that if we add 0 in front of the natural number it will not change it, but adding it in front of the decimal part of the real number will. Similarly, adding a zero to the right side of a natural number will change it, while adding a zero to the right side of a real number's decimal won't.

Knowing this, we can construct the bijection. First take the real number and reverse it. In our example of 0.123, this will become 321.0. Then, we can remove the .0, which leaves us with the number 321. This proves bijection of real numbers in range $[0, 1)$ and the set \mathbf{N} .

However, a problem arises which prevents us from using this method to relate every real number to exactly one natural number.

Consider numbers 1.27 and 0.127. Using the previous method they would both map to 72.

Here we see that due to the loss of information we cannot map every real number to exactly one natural number.

Chapter 2:

Mapping every real number to exactly one natural number

We need to, again, ask ourselves an important question: “How do the real numbers differ from the natural numbers?”

It is simple: They are composed of 2 parts. First is the whole part, which comes before the decimal point, and then the decimal part, which comes after.

It is trivial we can match the whole part to a natural number (negative numbers will be accounted for later), and we have just seen how we can relate any real number in range $[0, 1)$ to a natural number. That means that we can represent any real number with 2 natural numbers. If we label the whole part as W and the reverse decimal as D , we would get the real representation of $W.D$

The difference when looking at a real number compared to a natural is the point. It is what separates the W and D part of the number. The reason why we are unable to relate the real numbers to natural is clear once we look at the set of symbols which represent them.

N is made of symbols: $\{ 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 \}$

R is made of symbols: $\{ 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, . \}$

Let's label the **N** symbols as N_s , and **R** symbols as R_s .

Since R_s is larger than N_s , it is possible to create more permutations which represent the real numbers than permutations which represent the natural numbers. We can change this using a simple trick: We will look at the natural numbers in the base 11 representation (Note: we can either increase the base of **N** or decrease the base of **R**).

Now we get:

N is made of symbols: { 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, α }

R is made of symbols: { 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, . }

Now we have a way to represent the decimal point. We can now construct the W and D parts of a real number, and put α to act as a point.

So let's try this approach on an example. If we try to map the number 734657832.87563784 to a natural number using this method we will get:

W: 734657832

D: 48736578

And combined they look like: 734657832 α 48736578

It is important to recognize that adding α —that is, base shift—is just a notational trick, and quantitatively it represents a “jump” in the natural number's value. These “jumps” mean that, for example, going from number $1\alpha 9$ to number $1\alpha 10$ increases it by 2 instead of 1, since we are skipping the number $1\alpha\alpha$. This means that we have just successfully mapped all real numbers to one natural number, all while not using every natural number.

Increasing the base of natural numbers, as mentioned, is a notational trick. It does nothing to the meaning of a number (other than how we perceive it), and more importantly, the cardinality of the set **N**.

Note that negative numbers aren't a problem, since we can just increase the base and add another symbol to represent negation, which will be expanded upon in the following chapter.

Chapter 3:

Mapping every point in an n-dimensional space to a natural number

A point in 2-dimensional space can be represented using 2 real numbers (x and y coordinates). Since we have just established how each real number can be represented using a natural number, we notice that a point in 2-dimensional space can be represented using 2 whole numbers. We have also mentioned how real numbers are simply 2 whole numbers, which means their representation is the same as the representation of a point in 2-dimensional space. This means we can use the same method to represent that point as one natural number. So, for example, if we have the point (3.4, 2.6), we can represent it as $3\alpha 4\alpha 2\alpha 6$. We use the same symbol α for the separation of the x and y coordinate, which is fine because the first α will represent the separation of W and D of the x coordinate, the second α is the separator of the values of coordinates, and the third is the separator of W and D of the y coordinate. Alternatively, we can increase the base again and use another symbol to represent a coordinate separator.

As mentioned in the previous chapter, in order to represent negative coordinates we will use symbol β in front of the coordinate to represent negative values. So for example, point (-3.4, -2.6) will be represented as $\beta 3\alpha 4\alpha \beta 2\alpha 6$

Notice how nothing we applied is constrained to the second dimension, and we can easily extend this to the n -th dimension. In dimension n , the number of α digits will be $2n - 1$. Every even α acts as a coordinate separator, while every odd α acts as W-D separator. This can further be extended to matrices and tensors using a similar method.

Chapter 4:

Infinite incomparability theorem

Infinite incomparability theorem states:

Given two infinitely large sets A and B, it is possible to show that $|A| > |B|$.

Proof:

Let $A = \{ n_1, n_2, n_3, \dots \}$

Let $B = \{ m_1, m_2, m_3, \dots \}$

Assume $|A| < |B|$, that is, for every n_i in set A there exists a corresponding element m_i in set B which n_i does not map to, but for some infinitely many m_j elements in set B there does not exist a corresponding element n_j in set A.

Let us now make a list of every possible permutation of the elements of set B.

$m_g m_h m_j \dots$

$m_b m_a m_o \dots$

$m_h m_g m_x \dots$

$m_c m_k m_j \dots$

$m_o m_f m_v \dots$

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If we do the same to the set A we should get the number of permutations such that each permutation in set A can map to exactly one other permutation in set B—but not the other way—in a way that each set A's permutation's i -th element is the same as the the i -th element of the B's permutation it maps to. However, we can find a permutation which came from A that doesn't exist in B using the diagonal argument. First we write any element of set A which doesn't

map to the first element of the first permutation of set B. Then we write any element of set A which doesn't map to the second element of the second permutation of set B. We do so for every permutation, writing down an element from A which doesn't map to the i -th element of the i -th B permutation. What we get is a permutation of A which doesn't map to any permutation of B, showing how despite the B having a higher number of elements, A had more permutations than B, which means A had more elements than B, hence $|A| > |B|$. This is a contradiction to our assumption, so we conclude that $|B| > |A|$ is not possible.

But since the theorem accepts arbitrary sets of infinite size we can repeat the process after reversing the positions of A and B, resulting in $|A| > |B|$ being impossible.

If neither sets can be greater than another, that means they must be of the same size, hence $|A| = |B|$.

This theorem implies each and every infinity to be the same size.

This theorem shows how Georg Cantor got his false proof of $|[0, 1]| > |\mathbf{N}|$. Even if one shows that $|A| > |B|$ —where both sets are infinite—is true, we cannot prove that one is greater than the other.

Chapter 5:

Additional notes

This chapter contains topics I didn't find place for in earlier chapters, topics I wanted to elaborate, and help in understanding the infinity and why it behaves as it does.

It is possible to order numbers in range $[0, 1)$. Apply the inverse operation of what we did to get the D(reversed decimal part of a real number) in W.D representation of a real number. That means, if we take number 1 we can represent it as 0.1, number 2 as 0.2, number 478 as 0.874, and so on. Adding to this, it is possible to order each real number since they can be represented using natural numbers.

Similarly, it is possible to rearrange the set of natural numbers such that between every 2 natural numbers exists another natural number. For this we would use the same method as we did in obtaining D. So in the exact middle of numbers 1 and 2 would be number 51, because in the middle of numbers 0.1 and 0.2 exists number 0.15. This is simply rearranging the set, therefore the cardinality remains the same.

In the second chapter of the paper in order to map every real number to one natural we do not achieve bijection, but injection. In other words, we do not use every natural number. For example, no real number maps to the number $\alpha\alpha$ (1330 in base 10, or 1570 if we are using base 12 after adding the negation symbol β).

The **Infinite incomparability theorem** proves that no infinity is greater than another. Even if one 'proves' that there exist two infinitely large sets A and B such that $|A| > |B|$, **Infinite incomparability theorem** shows how it is also possible to prove $|B| > |A|$, leading to contradiction.

We have noticed it is possible to show both that $|\mathbf{N}| > |\mathbf{R}|$ and $|\mathbf{R}| > |\mathbf{N}|$.

The base change isn't the only way to map real numbers to natural ones. Another method is as follows: for a number $r \in \mathbf{R}$ we will take its W and D parts. We will then write the natural number the number r maps to in the following way:

Write the digits as $SW_1D_1W_2D_2\dots W_iD_i$ so that W_i is the i -th digit of the W (whole part of the real number), D_i the i -th digit of the D (reversed decimal part of the real number), and S either a 1 (representing a positive number) or a 2 (representing a negative number).

At first set \mathbf{R} seems obviously larger than set \mathbf{N} . To explain why it is not, let's tackle an easier comparison.

Let E be the set of all positive even numbers. It may seem that E contains half as many elements as set \mathbf{N} , but then we notice how every element $e \in E$ can be mapped to exactly one element $n \in \mathbf{N}$, such that $e = 2n$.

Despite E being a subset of \mathbf{N} , we can form a bijection. It is the same situation with set \mathbf{R} , only harder to imagine.

It is crucial to understand one thing about infinity: there is always another element. No matter how many elements we pair up, there will always be one which we haven't. Infinity is, by definition, infinite.